

THE EFFECT OF HORMONAL DRUGS USED DURING GESTATION ON THE HUMAN BODY.

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Abstract. This article focuses on research and development aimed at improving the treatment of enamel hypoplasia in children caused by hormonal drugs during pregnancy. It presents measures to identify the clinical and functional features of the specific treatment of diseases associated with diseases of the oral cavity in modern dentistry, developing in children as a result of hormonal drugs during pregnancy.

Keywords. Enamel hypoplasia, physiotherapy, clinic-dental, laboratory, immunological and statistical methods.

Enamel hypoplasia, which occurred in their children as a result of taking hormonal drugs during pregnancy, occupies a special place in its prevalence, complexity in diagnosis and treatment. Scientific sources note that "studies of the last two decades show that enamel hypoplasia in children caused by hormonal drugs during pregnancy is up to 42%, and together with various syndromes, these diseases account for up to 30%." This condition is explained by the fact that the initial stages of the disease proceed without pronounced symptoms, the lack of opportunity to obtain sufficient information about changes in both clinical and laboratory studies, as well as the lack of unified etiopathogenetic views among specialists. This indicates the need to improve the methods of treatment and prevention of the problem.

Worldwide, special attention is paid to research and development aimed at improving the treatment of enamel hypoplasia in children caused by hormonal drugs during pregnancy. At the same time, identification of clinical and functional features of the specific course of diseases associated with oral diseases in modern dentistry, developing in children as a result of hormonal drugs during pregnancy; assessment of the location of dental and physiotherapy measures in the process of complex treatment; of particular importance is the development of a plan for a comprehensive step-by-step approach that takes into account the somatic condition of children; the proposal of preventive treatment methods based on disorders of the functioning of the oral organs in children caused by hormonal drugs during pregnancy; improvement of the development of methods for evaluating the effectiveness of treatment.

In our country, targeted and practical measures are being taken to reform the health care system and equate it with world requirements, effective methods of prevention, early diagnosis and comprehensive treatment of diseases of the oral mucosa are being developed, scientific research is being conducted aimed at improving methods of diagnosis and treatment of enamel hypoplasia in children caused by hormonal drugs during pregnancy, in leading scientific centers and higher educational institutions of the world. at the Tashkent State Dental Institute.

As a result of the use of hormonal drugs during pregnancy, a number of scientific results have been obtained in research to improve the treatment of enamel hypoplasia of

childhood origin, including the importance of any disease in modern society is determined by the prevalence of this disease among the population, the severity and severity of the consequences, the economic losses of the patient and his family or society as a whole. Organizations report that it ranks 6th among dental diseases in terms of the prevalence of enamel hypoplasia in children caused by hormonal drugs during pregnancy. Enamel hypoplasia caused by hormonal drugs during pregnancy in children is also a problem for dentists because of its multifaceted effects on the body. Thus, in modern dentistry, an urgent problem remains the study of the effect of enamel hypoplasia on children as a result of hormonal drugs during pregnancy, and the prevention of complications of diseases.

The analysis carried out in the literature sources showed that the influence of enamel hypoplasia in children caused by hormonal drugs during pregnancy, issues of treatment and prevention of dental diseases are being studied. Carrying out a number of scientific research works devoted to the study of this problem indicates the imperfection of the traditional method of treating enamel hypoplasia in children and complications of the disease caused by hormonal drugs during pregnancy.

The reliability of the research results is confirmed by the use of modern, complementary clinical and dental, laboratory, immunological and statistical methods used in research work, obtaining children diagnosed with enamel hypoplasia caused by an insufficient amount of hormonal drugs during pregnancy, theoretical and practical confirmation of the presented results, their reliability in comparison with the data obtained by domestic and foreign validity of conclusions by foreign researchers, also on the basis of approval by authorized organizations. It is no secret that many expectant mothers who want to give birth to a healthy child react negatively to any pharmacological agents, including those that are allowed during pregnancy. However, this point of view is also considered erroneous, since during childbirth a woman may catch a cold or get hives, and conditions that may interfere with the normal course of pregnancy are not excluded.

Any drug during pregnancy should be prescribed by a doctor. However, sometimes there are situations when women are physically unable to seek advice from a specialist. At the same time, you need to know which pills can be used. Here is a list of permitted pregnancy medications: Antipyretics and painkillers in the form of paracetamol and ibuprofen.

- * Antiviral drugs in the form of Anaferon, Viferon, Arbidol.
- * Almagel phosphalgel is suitable for the treatment of heartburn.
- * Drotaverine is preferable among antispasmodics.
- * Loratadine should be considered as an antiallergic agent, but with caution.
- * Rehydration agent for oral dehydration-Rehydrone.
- * Enterosorbents for poisoning in the form of enterosgel, "Smekta", "neosmectin" and other drugs allowed during pregnancy.

However, the first thing a woman should do is immediately consult a doctor to assess the situation. The fact is that in some conditions, such as spotting from the genitals, severe abdominal pain, sudden bloating, a sharp increase in blood pressure, uncontrolled vomiting, diarrhea and fever, during the first visit to the doctor, you should ask him for a list of permitted drugs during pregnancy. Self-medication and taking medicinal plants are highly undesirable, since in this case the results are unpredictable. A cold is always unpleasant, and when a woman is expecting a child, it is problematic. At the same time, the question always arises, what kind of syrup tablets can be and which of them are prohibited. It's good when

ARVI passes without a high temperature, but what if the thermometer suddenly shows a large mark? How to safely get rid of the situation? The medicines allowed in the 1st trimester of pregnancy will be selected by a doctor.

Of course, the main shock from a cold should be inflicted with the help of folk remedies, only with herbal preparations you need to be careful, since some plants may be contraindicated, for example, juniper or strawberries. Favorite raspberry jam in tea is also not worth consuming, but it will have to be consumed a lot to cause serious harm. Do not steam your feet and do not make enemas. Complications in the form of secondary infections of the throat or nasopharynx should be avoided. The fact is that a runny nose can develop into sinusitis or sinusitis, and the cough itself can turn into pneumonia or bronchitis. Then a woman definitely cannot do without antibiotics, and this is the most necessary thing when wearing.

What drugs are allowed during pregnancy, you should find out in advance. The therapist should choose a cure for fever, in extreme cases it should be reduced with products containing paracetamol, which is a relatively safe remedy, unlike the same aspirin. The list of permitted cold medications for pregnant women is small. Medications allowed during pregnancy for colds and flu. Permission to use nasal sprays such as "milkweed composite", "Nazivin", "Pinosol beriladi.va Givalex in combination with oracept or Ingalipt serves as a suitable remedy for sore throat during pregnancy. You can also use drugs such as Bromhexine, Bronchicum (it should be used only in the first trimester), Stoptussin or Falimint will be suitable later. Do not take codeine syrups, this may lead to respiratory depression of the fetus.

The use of immunomodulators during influenza therapy should be discussed with a doctor, since the issue of their use is still controversial. Paracetamol can be used to reduce fever, and pinazol drops are perfect for nasal congestion. In this disease, chamomile tincture with soda solution or furacilin for gargling, as well as Pharyngosept tablets, helps well. Marshmallow root is used as an expectorant. Immunomodulators are one of the methods of treating flu during pregnancy, but you should consult your doctor before using them. Many expectant mothers use homeopathy in the form of Oscilloccinum and heel's Flu to treat this disease. Both of these drugs are allowed during pregnancy. As a remedy for the flu, while in a state, you can use folk remedies and herbal medicine. For example, antitussive remedies are compatible with inhalations with an infusion of calendula, essential oils, etc. Lemon tea or pink tea can also help a woman recover faster. Consider medications that are allowed for coughing in the 3rd trimester of pregnancy.

A cough that is accompanied by a sore throat and passes without sputum is called dry. This reflex is a symptom of colds and infectious pathologies and is very dangerous for pregnant women. This can cause pressure inside the uterus, which prevents the normal supply of oxygen to the fetus. Severe contractions of the uterus during coughing in the last months of pregnancy can lead to rupture of the amniotic sac, which will lead to premature birth. At the initial stage, such a symptom becomes the culprit of the threat of termination of pregnancy. As part of the fight against it, you can use pills that suppress the cough reflex. The task of tablets designed to treat such symptoms in pregnant women is to accelerate the formation and outflow of mucus. The best drugs are expectorants and mucolytics.

In the first trimester of pregnancy, doctors advise women to completely forget about headache pills. Many women manage to overcome this by ventilating the room and lying quietly without a pillow. Often, the unpleasant feeling improves immediately after sleep.

For some patients, self-massage of the temples and applying cabbage leaves or ice to the forehead helps. Sometimes a handkerchief or a handkerchief tightly tied on the head serves as an assistant. Infusions of mint, lemon balm and chamomile have a mild analgesic effect. If a woman has low blood pressure, sweet black tea can help increase it, thereby relieving headaches. In the following trimesters, paracetamol-based drugs will help stop such attacks. We are talking about Panadol and Efferalgane. These drugs are not addictive.

An approved drug for colds and flu during pregnancy, Panadol Extra, in addition to paracetamol, also contains caffeine, so it can be used at low blood pressure. But gynecologists can rarely use Panadol. The dosage recommended in the instructions should be followed. "No-shpa" also sometimes serves as a salvation, reducing vasospasm, lowering blood pressure and relaxing muscles. As for ibuprofen, it can be used during pregnancy only occasionally and up to the thirtieth week as an anesthetic. Let's find out which nasal congestion remedies are best to take. Oil drops are used to prevent the mucous membranes from drying out and reduce dryness and irritation, nasal congestion and swelling. These include, for example, a remedy called "Pinosol". Due to the presence of mint, rapeseed, pine and fir oil in the composition, this medicine relieves swelling, softens and stimulates local immunity. The drug is prohibited for women with allergies to the components and with the allergic nature of the common cold. Oxoline ointment is applied to the nasal passage to stimulate local immunity. Grippferon and Derinat are also suitable for these purposes. They act on the mucous membranes, stimulating the production of their own protective factor. Such drugs are used at any stage of pregnancy, strictly according to the instructions, the duration of use is not limited.

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